

FAIR Workflows to establish IGSN for Samples in the Helmholtz Association (FAIR WISH)

D4: Final harmonised metadata templates for terrestrial and aquatic Geo-Bio samples: changelog

Authors

Mareike Wieczorek (AWI)

Alexander Brauser (GFZ)

Linda Baldewein (Hereon)

Birgit Heim (AWI)

Kirsten Elger (GFZ)

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Change Log

The FAIR SAMPLES TEMPLATE is a metadata template for terrestrial and aquatic Geo-Bio samples that can be used for bulk description and transmission of sample metadata to be registered with IGSN and included in the sample catalogue.

This document summarises the changes from a prototype (D2; described in Wieczorek et al. 2022a) and Version 1.0 (D3: Wieczorek et al. 2022b) and Wieczorek et al. (2023a) to the current Version 2.0 of the FAIR SAMPLES TEMPLATE (Wieczorek et al. 2023b).

Section 1 summarises the changes that were made from the prototype (D2) to Version 1.0 (D3). Section 2 includes a detailed list of changes from the FAIR SAMPLES TEMPLATE v. 1.0 to v. 2.0, sorted by worksheet.

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1. Change Log Summary - D2 to version 1.0

1.1 Sample description

The first version of the sample description template, as described in Wieczorek et al. (2022a), had only one sheet for sample description. To allow for describing/ registering samples at different hierarchy levels in a single step/ document, the worksheets 'Parent' to 'Child3' were introduced in the FAIR SAMPLES TEMPLATE v. 1.0 (Wieczorek et al., 2023a). Consequently, further „SELECT” columns were added to the worksheet 'Guide' to allow users for flexible template generation where sample description worksheets 'Parent' to 'Child3' can be customised individually.

1.2 User experience

A worksheet “HowTo” was added to give users a brief handbook for the template that also includes a link to an online video tutorial (Wieczorek et al., 2022b). This worksheet includes (1) general instructions for sample metadata submission, (2) an overview of object categories that can be described using the template, (3) an explanation on how to use the “Guide” worksheet, and (4) an explanatory illustration of the general sample hierarchy.

For each variable in the sample description worksheets ('Parent' to 'Child3') links to the variable's definition in the 'Guide' were included. Links were also included in each worksheet with controlled vocabulary to bring users back to the 'Guide' or to one of the sample description sheets.

To minimise the risk of input errors that may break the tables, unused columns in the worksheets were hidden, the table appearance was restyled, and cells that do not require any input were protected.

1.3 Controlled vocabulary

Further sampling methods were added, which had been discussed with the community (marked in green). In the 'Material' vocabulary list the terms „snow“ and „Liquid > aqueous > porewater“ were added. However, value URIs for these terms have not been provided yet.

2. Change Log UserTemplate_FAIRWISH.xlsx (v. 1.0 to v. 2.0)

2.1 HowTo

- Changed title from 'IGSN – Data submission' to 'IGSN FAIR Sample Metadata Submission' to be more explicit.
- Revised explanation text by more explicit wording.
- Added figure 'Example Relationships of IGSN and Parent IGSN' to visualise parent-child relationships between different hierarchies.
- Added minor style elements to text and added alternative text to figures to improve readability.
- Added alternative text to figures to improve accessibility.

2.2 Guide

- Inclusion of the possibility to add more than one entry per cell where entries must be separated by semicolon for variables: 'Other Names', 'PI', 'Contributor' and 'Contributor type'.
- The selection of variables related to other variables, e.g., 'size unit' related to 'size', was partly automated to ensure rich and reusable metadata.
- Hid 'Related identifier type' and 'Relation type' to improve template usability as these variables are not being filled by users.
- Fixed input handling in „SELECT“ columns.

The number of metadata elements (n) for each category has changed as follows:

Category "**Sample**" (n=20 to n=22)

- Added variable 'Parent sample name' (-) to enable referencing a sample to a parent sample without IGSN (use case: before an IGSN has been assigned to a sample).
- Added variable 'Alternate material' (alternateMaterial) to allow for free text entries if no controlled vocabulary is available for the material.
- Added variable 'Classification' to allow classifying materials that are not "Rock", "Mineral", "Biological" or "Species".

Category "**Location**" (n=25 to n=26) Added "elevation end unit" to give further information on the end elevation in case of e.g. transects

- Added variable 'Site type' to more explicitly specify the type of a sampling site rather than the sample itself
- Removed variable 'Water body' and integrated the terms from ENVO Ontology (Buttigieg et al., 2016) into worksheet 'Landform'.

Category "**Reference**" (n=9 to n=3)

- Removed variables 'relatedIdentifierType' and 'relationType' as not being filled by users "Reference" (n=9 to n=3)

2.3 Parent, Child1, Child2, Child3

- Fixed bug in linked header rows.

2.4 SampleType

- Removed terms that further specify individual samples (e.g., "Plant") and sites (e.g., "Vegetation Plot"). Instead, controlled vocabulary was added to worksheets 'ClassificationBiology' and 'SiteType' was newly created.

2.5 SiteType

- Added this worksheet to distinguish different kinds of study areas.

2.6 ClassificationBiology

- Added terms from the BRENDA Tissue Ontology (BTO, Chang et al., 2021) to specify organism forms and parts of animals and plants.

2.7 Landform

- Added terms: fjord, lagoon, meteorite lake, pond, river, swamp ecosystem, thermokarst lake, tectonic lake from ENVO Ontology (Buttigieg et al., 2016).

2.8 Waterbody

- This worksheet was deleted and the terms were revised and partly moved to the worksheet 'Landform'.

2.9 Minor editions / user experience improvements:

- Added automatic selection of metadata elements that are related to the element above (e.g automatic selection of 'length_unit' when the property 'length' is selected by the user).
- Added alternative text to figures
- Cleaned data validation and error handling functionality in 'SELECT' columns.
- Revised definitions for variables 'IGSN' and 'Parent IGSN'.
- Hide unused cells and columns to improve template usability and security.
- Changed background of heading fields to lighter colours for better contrast and readability.
- Unified button sizes and cursor positions in all sheets.

3 References

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